

CULTURAL SCIENCES

JABRAİL: YESTERDAY AND TODAY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7391032>

Imamaliyeva N.,

Azerbaijan State University of Economics, student
ORCID: 0000-0002-0006-6179

Dargahzade S.

Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, student

This work was supported by the Science Development Foundation under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan: **Qrant № EIF-GAT-6-2021-2(39)-13/11/5-M-11**

Abstract

Jabrail region is one of the rich regions of Azerbaijan with historical, cultural and religious monuments. The name of the district is derived from the name of father Jabrail, who founded Jabrail villiage. The territories from Ziyarat Mountain to the Araz River belonged to Father Jabrail and his children. After the death of Father Jabrail, who loved his native land, he was buried on the land belonging to him, at the very top of Alpasha mountain, according to the custom of that time. Jabrail district, which has a great economic and tourism potential, is in the south of the Republic of Azerbaijan, in the southeast of the Lesser Caucasus mountains, on the left bank of the Araz river, borders with the Islamic Republic of Iran to the south, Zangilan to the southwest, Gubadli to the west, Khojavand to the north, and Fuzuli to the east. Located 434 meters above sea level, Jabrail region has ice springs, emerald forests, historical and cultural monuments, etc. occupies a unique position in the country with its territories. Before the Armenian Forces occupied Jabrail district, it was rich in cement, marble, sawstone and other valuable construction materials. It is known that there are even iron ore and oil deposits in the region. Before the occupation, the population was engaged in animal husbandry, grape growing, grain growing, and cocoon growing. The development of science, culture and education reached a high level here. Two years have passed since Jabrail region was liberated from occupation. Construction and restoration works will continue in the district.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Karabakh, Jabrail, monuments, sanctuaries, Khudafarin bridge

Jabrail district, which has a great economic and tourism potential, is in the south of the Republic of Azerbaijan, in the southeast of the Lesser Caucasus mountains, on the left bank of the Araz river, borders with the Islamic Republic of Iran to the south, Zangilan to the southwest, Gubadli to the west, Khojavand to the north, and Fuzuli to the east. Located 434 meters above sea level, Jabrail region has ice springs, emerald forests, historical and cultural monuments, etc. occupies a unique position in the country with its territories.

The name of the district is derived from the name of father Jabrail, who founded Jabrail village. The territories from Ziyarat Mountain to the Araz River belonged to Father Jabrail and his children. After the death of Father Jabrail, who loved his native land, he was buried on the land belonging to him, at the very top of Alpasha mountain, according to the custom of that time. Zur Aliyev, an employee of ANAS, doctor of political philosophy, gave extensive information about the construction of Father Jabrail and his shrine in his scientific article: "This mausoleum known as Father Jabrail" in the north of the village of Jabrail has a length 4.5 meters, a width 2.4 meters, and a height of 1.8 meters, traces of the grave and ancient settlements still remain. Jabrail father Mirzajan, Yarehmed, Shahvalad, Bunyad, Gurban, Khubiyar, Hasan and others. It is indicated in the sources that she has boys named later, the Jabrailli tribe was formed on his behalf. In the sources that talk about the Middle Ages, the famous Shahsevan, Javanshir, Afshar, etc. In addition to the tribes, the name of the Jabrayilli tribe is also mentioned.

When the Russian Empire compiled a list to collect taxes after the occupation (1823), it registered a population of 2200 people in Jabrayilli tribe with 17 divisions, 443 houses. In the second half of the 19th century and the 50s of the 20th century, Jabrail village was also called Kirakhdin. This was related to the creation of the "Quarantine" (forty days) department in Dashkasan village in 1831 and the transfer of that department to jabrail village in 1848. They pronounced it as "Grakhdin" because it was not familiar to the language of the local population. Historically, the territory of Jabrail was part of the states of Media (VII-V centuries BC), Achaemenid Empire (IV-III centuries BC), Albania (IV-III centuries BC). During the Albanian period, Jabrail territory was part of the districts called Pazkank, Ahrisn and Dizak" (1).

Jabrail region is one of the rich regions of Azerbaijan with historical, cultural and religious monuments. The sanctuaries, historical-religious, historical-architectural monuments located in Jabrail district are as follows:

1. **Jabrail district:** Khudafarin bridge with 11 arches, Khudafarin bridge with 15 arches
2. **Jabrail city:** Agoglan necropolis – early middle ages, Sultan Allahverdi bath – 19th century, Old cemetery – middle ages
3. **Khudyarli village:** Niftali mounds – bronze age

4. **Karkhulu village:** Karkhulu mounds and settlement – Bronze age, Old cemetery - XVII-XVIII centuries

5. **Mahmudlu village:** Janqulu mound, Gumtapa mound

6. **Shikhlar village:** Imangazan hills, Shikhlar cave-Stone Age, Round tomb-XIV, Shaharcik village ruins-Middle Ages, Pottery settlement-Middle Ages, Old cemetery-Middle Ages, Stone ram figure

7. **Shikhli village:** Shikhli barrows – late bronze age, Imangazantapa barrows – late bronze age

8. **Galacik village:** Galadag fortress and settlement – early Middle ages, Masjdtapa mound – bronze age

9. **Naftalilar village:** Naftali mounds – late bronze age, age and early Iron age

10. **Kishlaq village:** Kishlaq mounds and settlement – late bronze age and early iron age

11. **Horovlu village:** Horovlu mounds – late bronze age and early iron age, Jinlitapa settlement – early iron age

12. **Shekarbeyli village:** Toragay hill settlement – first bronze age

13. **Javahirlar village:** Divler palace

14. **Khubyarli village:** Round tomb-XVII century, Octagonal tomb -XVII century

15. **Sirik village:** Castle tower, Old cemetery – middle ages

16. **Diridag Mountain:** Maiden's Castle-XII century, Old cemetery and settlement – middle ages

17. **Mountain Tumas village:** Sardaba-XIII-XIV century, Cave-middle ages, Tumas-ata

18. **Chalabilar village:** Mosque

19. **Papi village:** Mosque-XIX century

20. **Dashkasan village:** Mosque

21. **Mazra village:** Mosque-XIX century

22. **Suleymanli village:** Mosque-XIX century

23. **Hasanli plain:** Hasanli settlement – Middle Ages” and so on. (2, 119).

Before the Armenian Armed Forces occupied Jabrail district, it was rich in cement, marble, sawstone and other valuable construction materials. It is known that there are even iron ore and oil deposits in the region. Before the occupation, the population was engaged in animal husbandry, grape growing, grain growing, and cocoon growing. The development of science, culture and education reached a high level here. There were 92 doctors, 432 mid-skilled medical workers in 510-bed hospitals, more than 1,660 teachers in 72 schools, 3 music schools, 12 cultural houses, 32 clubs, 10 cultural tents, auto clubs and 508 cultural workers working in the region. There were more than 20,000 exhibits in Jabrail's History and Local History Museum. There were also 8 industrial enterprises, 42 collective farms, fattening association of large and small horned cattle, poultry factory.

Jabrail district, consisting of 1 city, 4 settlements and 97 villages, was occupied by the Armenian Armed Forces on August 23, 1993. Jabrail district have settled in up to 2,000 settlements in 58 districts of the Republic, including refugee camps, freight wagons and dormitories. As a result of the occupation, the region was damaged in the amount of 13.928 billion US dollars. 1050 sq. the territory of the district with a population of 52,000 people and 72 general education schools, 8 hospitals, 132 historical monuments, 150 cultural centers, and about 100 villages in these areas were brutally destroyed by the occupation of Armenians. “Divler palace” cave and “Başikesik dome” located near Daghtumas villageç ühich are material and cultural monuments of the region; “Mosque Hill”, “Canqulu” and “Gumtapa” mounds in Galacik village; Mazannene on the mountain of Diri, archeological, “Maiden's Castle” such as marble grandmother's tombs; “Castle” in the village of Sirik; Bridges of Khudafarin, Mosque complex in Çalabilar village, “Sultan Majid bath” in the center of the district, “Round tomb” in Shikhlar village, “Circular” 8-cornered tombs and mausoleums in Khubyarli village, tombs and mausoleums in the Turkish cemetery were all completely destroyed or damaged during the occupation is left.

The Khudafarin bridge, which is considered a symbol of Azerbaijan, is also located in Jabrail district. The Khudafarin bridge, which has important military and strategic importance, connects the medieval cities of South Azerbaijan and North Azerbaijan. The bridge built over the caravan road was built in the area of the Araz river surrounded by rocks. The bridge witnessed the occupation of Jabrail by Armenia in 1993, the liberation of Jabrail from occupation on October 4, 2020, and several historical events.

Corresponding member of ANAS, professor Jafar Qiyasi, in his scientific article “Khudafarin – longing bridge”, made notes about the architectural structure and materials of Khudafarin bridge: “Since the supports of the Great Khudafarin bridge are built on natural rocks lined up in the river bed, its arch spans are of different sizes. The plan of the bridge was not straight, but slightly curved, because the overhangs were thrown according to the natural structure of the rocks. The bridge, which is about 200 meters long, has a width of 4.5 meters, the largest arch span is more than 10 meters, and the greatest height on the river surface is about 10 meters. Since the upper surface of the bridge has a slight slope to the sides, its volume is fully adapted to the existing terrain. The breakwaters on the big bridge are made of well-hewn stones. The archivolts of the arches of the 15 spans of the bridge have a pointed shape, which is typical for the architecture of the Muslim period. The rest of the bridge is made of unhewn riverstone. The bridge railings on the overpass are made of baked brick. The texture and color compatibility of the building materials gave the great Khudafarin bridge a clear tectonic structure and a distinctive artistic appearance” (3, 14).

Below is a picture of Khudafarin Bridge before the occupation:

Khudafarin bridge (4, 22)

Locally important Haji Garaman shrine is located in Çalabilar village of Jabrail district. Here is the grave of that person, and on the tombs there is a text written in the Arabic alphabet. The sanctuary is surrounded by various stones, people who come to visit say prayers and tie their vows to small tree bushes. After prayers, they would circle three times at the head of the grave. Haji Garaman shrine is known not only in Azerbaijan, but also in Eastern countries. It has been mentioned in various sources that haji Garaman Çalavi moved from Diyarbakir city of Turkey to Jabrail district. The cemetery where haji Garaman was buried became sacred like a hearth. Haji Garaman name is taken from the Garaman tribe.

The Maiden's Castle is one of our next monuments which was subjected to Armenian vandalism. "The walls of the Maiden's Castle on the top of Diridag were 50 meters long and 13 meters high" (5). The castle, which is currently in ruins, was built for defense purposes. As a result of the invasion, the castle was completely blown up and destroyed.

During the period of Jabrail occupation, our underground and surface resources were looted by Armenians. Natural monuments, springs and aprings were subjected to natural erosion and destroyed. "Eastern sycamores, which are 1600 and 700 years old, in the village of Karkhulu, 200 years old, 900 and 750 years old in the village of Fungali, and more than 500 years old in the villages of Horovlu and Ishikli, were protected in Hajili village of Jabrail region. Armenian vandals, who destroyed our cities and villages, and our historical monuments, also destroyed the Eastern plane trees, which are considered natural monuments" (6).

On September 27, 2020, our noble army under the leadership of Commander-in-Chief Mr. Ilham Aliyev captured the villages of Buyuk Marjanli and Nwzgar of Jabrail district, on October 3 the villages of Mehdili, Chakhirli, Ashagi Maralyan, Shaybey and Quyjag, on October 4 the city of jabrail and 9 villages of the district – He freed the villages of Karkhulu Shukurbeyli, Cheraken, Dashkasan, Horovlu, Mahmudlu, Jafarabad, Yukhari Maralyan and Decal from occupation. As a result of the military operations in the region, a total of 1 city (Jabrail) and 80 villages were liberated from occupation.

After the end of the Patriotic War, on November 16, 2020, President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev and First Vice-President Mehriban Aliyeva visited the liberated Jabrail district. Within the framework of the visit, Mr. President Ilham Aliyev raised the flag of Azerbaijan in the city of Jabrail and Khudafarin Bridge. On November 26, 2020, according to the decree of the head of the country, the medal "for the release of Jabrail" was established. The military personnel who participated in the liberation of jabrail were awarded medals.

On October 4 of last year, the head of our state, Mr. President Ilham Aliyev, who visited Jabrail, visited the joint service center of "KAMaz" OJSC and "Ganja Automobile Plant" production union, the "Araz Valley Economic Zone" Industrial Park to be established in the East Zangazur economic district, the district's central Hospital, the school building. Laid the foundations of the first multi-apartment residential neighborhood in Jabrail. Later, the head of the country participated in the opening of the 110/35/10 KV "Jabrail" substation, the military unit complex of the state Border Service, and laid the foundation stone for the restoration of the Jabrail Memorial Complex and the city of jabrail.

Two years have passed since Jabrail region was liberated from occupation. The people of Azerbaijan never came to terms with the occupation Justice has already found its place. Construction and restoration works will continue in the region. We are sure of this and we believe Mr. President Ilham Aliyev. We can now say with complete ease – Jabrail is Azerbaijan! Karabakh is Azerbaijan!

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